

RELATIVE DENSITY, Building Dialogues

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Building Value

The value of a home is often calculated by a straightforward ratio of construction cost per square metre to the sale value of the completed dwelling per square metre. This is the metric used by the mortgage market in Ireland and for homeowners, this calculation can influence their decision to build, extend, alter, or upgrade their homes. Within architectural discourse, by contrast, there is a constant evolution in the understanding of value with the question of material value dominating current conversations. The trickling down of this discourse into the reality of small practice takes time. Pragmatic considerations will, of course, outweigh ideological ones when it comes to modest homes and budgets. This is exacerbated in the context of rural Ireland where the influence of an architect is rare. In recent projects, our focus and that of our clients has shifted. As material, labour and energy costs have increased and running costs have become a priority, there is a new emphasis on thermal performance, energy efficiency and spatial quality over quantity.

This paper reflects on three rural domestic projects undertaken between 2019 and 2024. The three projects are connected by their rural setting; by a desire to return to closer living conditions, intergenerational and communal plans for living more densely together; by a re-evaluation of the materials and structures already existing on a site; and by an openness to sharing resources and infrastructure.

All of these techniques are not new, in fact, they are a return more than a departure.

We assist our clients in understanding, illustrating and eventually building what they need. This process happens iteratively in each project and drawing as a tool is central to this process. We use overlays, we make notes, we demonstrate inhabitation, we try to show how people might live by drawing over plans and sections, bringing architectural drawings to life so that someone unused to reading a demolition plan, for example, can imagine themselves into the space. We use the live line over the hard line. In client meetings, we draw strategy and detail in different corners of the same page; dimensions to legal boundaries and the best spot for evening sun, a suggested view or a new spatial adjacency within the plan.

For each project, we have used an isometric viewpoint that shows the project and its immediate surroundings as a base layer. This overview, or birdseye view, gives a sense of the whole and, to an extent, can suggest the passing of time. In each project, other narratives, traditions and possibilities emerge through conversation, visits, drawings and the sharing of photographs with our clients. Beyond the practical or economic consideration of value, family ties and an

affinity to place strengthen client motivation. Family stories, patterns of living, experiences and ways of being that are valuable to our clients and that we can give a sense of weight to, come to the surface. The various strands can be edited and combined to create a new narrative for the project. Through these three projects, we present our changing mode of interacting with clients in order to build upon and inform their connection to place. We also present our changing attitude to the value of built fabric and the demands that we place upon it.

Montpelier - Filling in

2019-2021

O'Briensbridge-Montpelier, County Limerick, is a village in the southwest of Ireland. It developed in the typical, rural, Irish pattern, with houses on individual plots dispersed along a busy, secondary road. Situated on the east bank of the River Shannon, the land is generally flat and used for cattle grazing. The climate is one of mild summers and winters, with frequent rain.

At first, our instructions were to design a new house for a single family. Over time, the brief changed and we were asked to rework an existing single dwelling into a multi-generational family home to accommodate both the young family and their grandfather. The change in direction from new-build towards the renovation and reconfiguration of an existing house was influenced by a government

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Image 1: Demolition isometric drawing indicating fabric removed from Montpelier project and existing thematic annotations.

Image 2: Proposed isometric drawing indicating alterations to Montpelier project and thematic annotations.

grant-aided retrofit scheme and an expectation that upgrading an existing property would be faster and cheaper than building a new structure.

On a slightly elevated site, we found a bungalow that was typical of 1970s Irish pattern-book construction. It comprised a simple gabled roof structure, uninsulated concrete blockwork walls on minimal strip foundations, and an uninsulated concrete floor slab. External finishes included sand and cement render, imitation stone cladding and asbestos slate roof. The main house and garage had been connected by an ad hoc extension. The house and its later additions had been built by the grandfather of the family.

Within a footprint of 125 square metres of habitable accommodation and 25 square metres of garage, we had to allow for privacy and retreat, as well as shared utilities for three generations of the family. As is typical of Irish bungalows of this era, the existing layout was convoluted; a long, dark, turning corridor occupied the centre of the floorplan. Keeping a structural spine under the existing ridge beam, the layout was reconfigured to make shared living spaces from which private quarters could be accessed by grandfather, child and parents. Bedrooms address the east-facing rear garden, with south and west-facing living rooms to the front.

By reinforcing the existing ceiling joists in places, additional mezzanine spaces could be stacked over new living spaces. This was a way of ‘using’ structure to add space that is not habitable in the regulatory sense but allows for

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Images 3,4: Existing living room and exterior elevation of Montpelier, Images 5,6: Demolition stage showing strip out of ceiling boards and removal of internal blockwork partitions. Image 7: Construction stage showing new internal timber frame linings. Image 8: View from family living space towards Grandfather's living space with opening to playspace above Image 9: View from Grandfather's living space towards kitchen and family living space Image 10: Construction stage, exterior elevation.

expansive use by occupants; of building densely in a very constrained situation. These spaces cannot be listed as rooms by estate agents and therefore do not contribute in a definite way to an increase in property value. They were, however, one of the elements of the design that captured the imagination of our clients. By opening up and revealing the existing structure and by demonstrating how it might be inhabited, our clients became invested in building in an interconnected way; where not every function requires complete enclosure; where spatial relationships are informal and overlap; and where relatives can be apart from, but close to, the main activity of the house.

Through the careful rearrangement of the internal rooms, we created a home that responds directly to the sun's path. Doing so within the footprint of the existing house ensured efficiencies during the planning and construction stages but it is notable in the Montpelier isometric drawing that the approach to the wider landscape is confined to the boundary of the site. The alterations begin and end at the driveway entrance. In retrospect, there was scope to consider wider connections, particularly to neighbouring fields and outbuildings in the family's ownership.

The Story of a Structure

In the existing house, there was no heritage value in the conventional sense but during conversations with the family, the grandfather spoke of the physical work involved in pouring the foundations; the wheelbarrows that he filled and pushed; and the blocks he unloaded and lifted. These

tangential anecdotes added to the myth of the house. There was a direct memory of work, of physical exertion. While the decisions to keep parts of the structure were pragmatic, the testimony of its original builder was deployed, on occasion, to negotiate with a reluctant contractor.

Given that the original construction had no formal heritage value, and encouraged by the availability of government retrofit grants, we took what is the standard approach to improving thermal comfort in Ireland: adding layers of insulation, improving U-values and airtightness and installing energy-efficient mechanical systems¹. Questions of comfort were not specific and the ambition for the Building Energy Rating (BER)² was more clearly stated than that of the environmental design. The tangible indicators of performance, such as air tightness testing, were useful as targets that could be understood by the client and clearly met by the contractor. However, the limitations of the BER rating system have become apparent in this project post-completion. While it is unarguably efficient in terms of heat load, the homeowners struggle to achieve a comfortable internal temperature on the hottest days of summer. Having conversations with our clients post-occupancy, the question arises; what is a new vernacular in the Irish bungalow

1 The Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI) is an Irish government body established to promote and aid in the development of sustainable energy in Ireland. The National Retrofit Plan sets out how the Government will deliver on the Climate Action Plan targets of retrofitting the equivalent of 500,000 homes to a BER of B2/cost-optimal and installing 400,000 heat pumps in existing homes to replace older, less efficient heating systems by the end of 2030. The focus of the SEAI and the grants it provides is on achieving high thermal performance and airtightness targets and increasing renewable energy sources.

2 Building Energy Rating (BER) allows prospective buyers or tenants to objectively compare the energy performance of different dwellings on a like-for-like basis. It is an indicator of a home's energy efficiency and can be used to estimate the running costs and carbon emissions associated with heating the home to a comfortable level.

that balances energy efficiency with a responsive and considered approach to the living environment and the fabric that contains it?

The narrative that emerged from this process was one of a family creating a multigenerational home within the house that the grandfather built. A series of constraints were translated into something more idealistic. The 'granny flat' is a typical proposal but it is usually outside the envelope of the original, an annexe. Our clients had a pressing need to live together and because there was an idea of rehabilitation of the family home, the purpose, the narrative of the project was enough to outweigh the sense that we were constrained by the existing dimensions, by the container of the original house.

Annaholty - Stripping Back

2019-present

Annaholty, County Tipperary, is a townland in the southwest of the country. Located on the edge of a flat bogland, it is bisected by a motorway connecting Limerick City to Dublin. Sitka spruce plantations and a patchwork of grazing fields make up the remainder. Like the neighbouring County Limerick, the climate is mild and wet, protected by its inland location.

The old road that connected market towns along the route

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Image 11: Demolition isometric drawing indicating fabric removed from Annaholty project and existing thematic annotations.

Image 12: Proposed isometric drawing indicating alterations to Annaholty project and thematic annotations.

from Limerick to Dublin also cuts through the townland. Along this historic road, we found a traditional farmyard around which stood a stone byre to the east, a stone farmhouse to the west and a mature orchard to the north. The buildings are approximately 150 years old. Our client, an only son, lived in the house with his parents until 2002 when he built his own home on the adjoining site. His father passed away in 2015, followed by his mother in 2020. Our brief was to intervene in the existing fabric in order to extend the life of the house for another generation. In discussing his decision to renovate the house, our client spoke of his responsibility to ancestors and to descendants. For him, the buildings represented generations of connection to place. With this affinity for the place, the history and the fabric of the buildings already had an established value.

Taking the house and outbuildings as a whole, we proposed to restore the farmyard as the focus of a cluster of buildings with the farmhouse as a main dwelling and further accommodation in the renovated byre. Extending the living accommodation into the byre meant that minimal new fabric was required. A new wastewater treatment system was sized to fit in the orchard and the surface of the farmyard was made permeable to deal with stormwater. A garage was adapted to become a winter garden, taking advantage of its south orientation and a new extension made the existing agricultural buildings habitable. Small additions had been made to the house throughout the 1980s. One of these, a two-storey rear extension, had been built with concrete blocks and minimal foundations; we proposed to raise the

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Image 13: Photo of house taken in the 1970s
Image 14: Existing view of Byre building and farmyard
Image 15: Existing Kitchen interior
Image 16: Demolition stage showing strip out of internal wall paneling and cement plaster
Image 17: Temporary works showing existing roof timbers
Image 18: Construction stage showing new roof structure

Image 19: Timberframe addition to existing 1980's blockwork extension.

roof and use it as entry, circulation and bathroom spaces.

The question of usefulness and intergenerational thinking was extended to the land around the house. We saw our role here as identifying existing pathways and connections so that they could be reinforced and overlaid with new ones. The client and buildings are notable for the timeline they appear to inhabit. There was an unspoken confidence that the buildings' 150-year history could result in at least the same chronology again and that any plans and decisions we made during the project should be conscious of that legacy.

The Story of Fabric

Our approach was to return the house to something close to its vernacular form. The perceived significance or value of the stone buildings allowed us to propose natural materials, breathable and low-carbon, in our treatment of the existing fabric. The 1980s fabric was perceived as being less valuable and, as a result, we assumed that it should be brought up to current standards of thermal performance. However, on discovering the inadequacies of the foundations in the 1980s construction, we were forced to revisit our assumptions about what we were asking of this fabric. Adding 30cm of insulation, for example, placed too great a demand on its construction. It also raised questions about how we define comfort. We did not expect to bring the stone construction up to current regulatory U-values but with the work we were doing we expected an improvement in comfort by addressing the dew point, humidity, draughts

and so on. The reworked 1980s extension was to contain stairs and bathrooms, the question then became; what level of comfort is acceptable here? Should we work towards a 22 degrees Celsius steady temperature and 50% humidity, or can a warm floor and increased light levels result in an environment that is perceived as comfortable?

While a sensitive conservation approach to the original stone house was never in question, the 1980s blockwork addition invited questions and discussions about material value and maintenance. In our original design, we operated on an overly dualistic model and it was only during conversations on-site with our client that we were able to discuss and illustrate a potential spectrum of interventions, standards and environmental conditions. The question became more nuanced; what has an existing structure done during its lifetime and can it continue to do that job adequately?

In the end, the blockwork was retained but with fewer demands placed on it in terms of performance. The roof structure was considered in the same way. The structural engineer was satisfied with its integrity. Our client, however, took a longer view; if this is a one-in-one-hundred-year project, can the existing timber be expected to last another hundred years? The decision was taken to replace the roof rafters but the timber was retained for use as internal partition walls. The material remained on site, now in a supporting role rather than a structural one.

Our client's clear sense of purpose and responsibility to the place was particularly formative for our practice in finding

more varied reasoning when inviting discussion and making decisions. What started as a tongue-in-cheek mythology of building at Montpelier became, at Annaholty, a genuine appreciation of the significance of family ties and of the work of place-making. This was underpinned by a formal sense of value in the built heritage of the farm. During the project we started to record our clients' words, his passing anecdotes and testimonies, as the weight of this oral history in the project became apparent.

Lappanduff - Layering Up

2020-present

Lappanduff is a rural townland in County Cavan, the northwest of Ireland. It is set at an altitude among drumlin hills that are characteristic of this part of the country. The surrounding land is agricultural with a mix of dairy, livestock and forestry. The southwesterly prevailing wind is strong and persistent. The existing buildings adjacent to the site were constructed between 1980 and the present day. They include a cluster of agricultural sheds in concrete and steel frame along with the existing family farmhouse, a 1980s bungalow in cavity wall construction. This 1980s farmhouse had been built close to the main road for convenience and the less accessible historic settlement that had been the focus of the farm since the early 1800s was left for use as storage and eventually abandoned. As at Annaholty, this project was for the next generation in a farming family.

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Image 20: Proposed isometric drawing indicating alterations to Lappanduff and thematic annotations.

Image 21: Demolition isometric drawing indicating fabric removed from Lappanduff project and existing thematic annotations.

In this case, however, our client was also taking on the operation of the dairy farm.

Our client came to us with a brief to build a new house on an elevated, green-field site. We produced some sketch designs but were conscious of the pattern of leaving older structures behind and making new buildings without a plan for the old. We suggested building inside an underused hayshed near the current farmhouse instead. Our thinking about found structures had also evolved to become more inclusive. In this project, pragmatic considerations were used to justify the re-evaluation of existing materials rather than the other way round; on a farm, when inclement weather prohibits most outdoor jobs the shed facilitates work. In this case, it represents an opportunity to build economically. Its value is not as structure but as skin. At Lappanduff we found an empty shell, waiting to be tempered and occupied.

The form of the shed was typical of mid to late 20th-century agricultural buildings. Its light steel and timber frame was inadequate for re-use as a load-bearing structure. We proposed instead that it could function as a self-supporting rain-screen around a newly built insulated timber frame dwelling. The footprint of the new construction was offset internally from the perimeter of the shed so that its existing foundations could remain intact. A highly insulated raft foundation with a prefabricated timber-frame superstructure was proposed. Snow and wind loads were discounted from the calculations for this structure because the shed provides the outer skin. The insulated raft acts as

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Image 22: Existing shed shown in context
Image 23: Existing shed interior
Image 24: Excavation of shed floor to required levels
Image 25: Preparation of compacted hardcore and sand blinding
Image 26: Setting out of raft slab relative to existing shed
Image 27: Installation of EPS insulation formwork
Image 28: Reinforcement mesh ahead of concrete pour.

the structural slab and internal floor finish. The 40cm thick prefabricated timber frame was pre-insulated with densely compacted straw. Once the new structure is complete, portions of the shed skin will be replaced with translucent and transparent panels. Demolition in this case will be our last step instead of our first.

The current farmhouse, where our client lives with his parents, is twenty metres north of the shed. In the proposed site layout, its existing front garden will be shared by both homes, ensuring that agricultural land remains agricultural. In return, the new house offers spaces that are currently lacking or compromised in the old: a dedicated farm office, spaces for drying clothes and carrying out repairs, greenhouse growing in the sheltered interstitial zones. New planting and pathways formalise the connection between the new and old farmhouses and to the farmyard beyond.

The Story of Shelter

Over the course of the project, momentum has built around what is possible now that the shed has become a workshop for building a home. From the first suggestion of a new house on a hill, a shared excitement has developed in what we might think of as the *future story* of the project. The process, the inversion of the existing structure, our client, the local planners, neighbours and builders all have surrendered to the future storytelling of how a house could be built in a shed. The management of a farm requires many-sided competence including basic construction skills,

so a certain amount of self-build was possible here. The limited budget also suggested an element of self-build. The client's initial resistance softened through a combination of offsite prefabrication, separate subcontracts for more challenging elements of work and simple, straightforward detailing. For our client, the structure of the shed has become familiar; the construction period is the first phase of its inhabitation and time spent there builds confidence in the decision to retain it. An array of curious visitors including neighbours, architects and industry suppliers have further confirmed its value.

Existing structures are generally perceived by building contractors as obstacles to progress. Their off-plumb and uneven surfaces can add time, complexity and cost to a project. New construction, by contrast, is considered fast and straightforward. With Lappanduff our question was simple; can the existing structure have value at each stage of the project, including during construction?

Like a Russian doll, the proposed house is nested within the existing shed's structural frame. They do not touch. By offsetting the insulated fabric from the existing steel frame, we were able to address the question of thermal comfort as though it were an entirely new build house. In the spaces between skin and structure, a new range of environmental conditions are found, allowing a soft transition between house and weather-world. As in Montpelier, there are mezzanine spaces that reconnect to the central living spaces, so that even within a new structure there is a dense layering

of spatial connections. As in Annaholty, the existing structure is assessed on the basis of its past and future function; the demands placed on it remain realistic.

Building Stories

Our aim here has been to review three projects and investigate an emerging need and desire for density of inhabitation, of use and of material. By graphically retracing our decisions and their factors of influence in a single isometric drawing we became aware of an overarching narrative for each project. We realised that we build stories.

We think that our drawings should communicate both the ‘what’ and the ‘why’ of design decisions. When our clients do not see themselves as agents of change in how we build now, what can we say, and draw, to galvanise their interest and support in finding new construction methodologies and new ways of measuring value? Taking on our *rough work*, our live line, as a purposeful part of our drawing methodology is one way in which the story of the building and the construction language of the design might merge. Where previously an overlay drawn in haste, in conversation, would have been discarded, this has become a record of the process of client interaction.

Looking back at our shift in thinking over the course of these three projects, the weight of our clients’ words and observations has been significant. It is a conversation, then, that allows any project to happen. We build a story with our

clients that gives weight to particular aspects of their brief and leads to an understanding of needs and possibilities.

In previous evaluations of projects, we have reverted to a typical narrative where we, The Architects, want to achieve something and The Client, to a degree, must be convinced; The Builder, cajoled. We have presented projects as having a linear narrative. Our conclusion here, however, is that all of these characters can be overstated and underestimated. We want to move towards an inclusive history of a project where the contribution of all of those involved is captured and understood. We also recognise that the narrative is rarely linear, that there are fragments of ideas, anecdotes and solutions to problems on site that combine to make a building. Setting out on new projects, we are now alert to the potential of these fragments; we collect them, we feed them back into conversation.

In these three project stories, we identified a series of themes that are common to each and that might allow us to focus on this idea of building densely, intensely; that the value of the structure of a building can be extended in unexpected ways, ways that it was not designed for; that the value of the fabric of a building should not be diminished by its limitations; and that, at home, a sense of comfort and shelter outweighs almost all other considerations. These themes, these questions of value and shelter are often intangible. Through drawing and conversations, we will continue trying to resolve them in buildings.

Practices in Research #05 - Demolitions and Deconstructions - December 2024

Online Open Access Double-Blind Peer-Reviewed Journal for Practice-Based Research in Architecture

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Thanks to Orfée Grandhomme & Ismaël Bennani

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ISSN: 2736-3996

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